

Anonymisation plan – Quantitative research example

General information

Dataset name	Placement Monitoring of Graduates from the University of Tampere.
Creator(s) of the plan	Annika Sallinen
Responsible person(s)	Maija Majava, Pentti Raccoon
Project summary	<p>Tampere University Career Services has monitored the employment of recent graduates through studies examining the employment situation of Tampere University graduates approximately one year after graduation.</p> <p>The questions in the material deal with the work situation and work history, factors affecting employment, and satisfaction with the work situation, degree, and alumni activities. The background variables are mainly the same in each dataset.</p>
Related sources	<p>Information on the persons belonging to the respondent group can be found e.g. in social media (e.g. social media accounts, group memberships, LinkedIn), and master's theses are often available on university websites with author and field of study information. In addition, information on the number of students can be found in Education Statistics Finland, where the numbers can be examined by university and by age, nationality, field of study and gender. If an intruder suspects that a person is studying at a university, he or she can check with the university's student affairs office, and the information must be provided if the person has given permission to do so. For an external person, it may be possible to identify an individual by combining data from the dataset with information obtained from outside. This is possible, for example, with the help of social media data. Facebook provides information about the major subject, university, year of start of studies, gender, current and former jobs, educational institutions, and place of residence.</p>

Population and sampling

Population	The population of the annual data series consists of persons with a higher university degree or a Doctor’s degree at the University of Tampere who graduated about a year ago from the time of the survey. The data on the population for each year should be viewed in Education Statistics Finland. Here the number of students can be viewed by university, field of study, gender, year of commencement of studies, nationality and age.
Sampling	The survey is a total dataset and the response rate has varied in different years, always exceeding 50 per cent.
Rare phenomenon	From the perspective of anonymisation, particular attention should be paid to the size and gender distribution of fields of education. For example, in 2016, the number of attainers of higher university degrees was 1139. The number of graduates by field of education varies from 42 graduates in information technology and communications (ICT) to 462 graduates in social sciences. The gender distribution is very uneven, for example only 4 men graduated from health sciences in 2016.

Dataset age

Age	FSD has data since 1998 and the newest ones are from 2024.
Change over time	In the case of the oldest datasets, it can be assumed that the data studied have changed. However, all materials are anonymised with the same accuracy, because career information about graduates in the 90s can be expected to be found online, for example on LinkedIn.

Information value

Significant information	From the point of view of the usability of the data, it is important to try to leave numerical variables intact. Of the numerical indirect identifiers, the aim is to leave the most relevant ones, which in this study are gender and field of education. From a research point of view, it may be interesting to leave the citizen variable in order to be able to study foreign students, but since their number is relatively small by field of study, the variable may include an identification risk.
Irrelevant information	Open variables can be sacrificed.

Identifiers in the dataset

Identifier	Di ¹	In ²	Se ³	Decision whether to anonymise, chosen anonymisation technique and rationale ⁴
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Randomised. If the gender distribution in any field has been uneven <5 during the year of graduation in question, the variables or observation values must be adjusted. Values can be deleted if there are enough similar values already in place. If the former is not possible, another alternative to anonymisation is mixing the data, i.e. changing members of the majority sex to the opposite sex or changing a minority to the majority gender. E.g. if three men graduated in health science in 2010, two of whom responded to the survey, the values can be changed to women if there are relatively more female graduates. When randomising methods are used, the effects on statistical analyses should be limited. For downstream users, it is good to mention that in the data, two men have been changed to women due to the small number of men.
Field of education or Degree	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Classified to assure enough respondents for each field of study, degree and unit. E.g. master's degrees in theatre work have been combined with master's degrees in humanities in the same category, because theatre work only admits a small number of students and is a field in which recognition is high due to the publicity of actors. For the same reason psychology is combined with the field of social science and health science is combined with medicine.
Degree programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. The anonymity of graduates is best maintained by limiting information about the degree programme, as when combined with other information, they provide information about the graduate that is too individual.

¹ Direct identifiers refer to Information that is sufficient on its own to identify an individual includes a person's full name, social security number, email address containing the personal name, and biometric identifiers (fingerprints, facial image, voice patterns, iris scan, hand geometry or manual signature).

² Indirect identifiers (or quasi-identifiers) are the kind of information that on their own are not enough to identify someone but, when linked with other available information, could be used to deduce the identity of a person. Background variables and indirect identifiers include, for instance, age, gender, education, status in employment, economic activity and occupational status, socio-economic status, household composition, income, marital status, mother tongue, ethnic background and place of work or study. Indirect identifiers relating to region of residence include, for example, postal code, neighbourhood, municipality, and major region. Date can also be an indirect identifier. Date of birth is the most common example, but dates of death and dates of newsworthy events may also be indirect identifiers in research data when combined with other information.

³ Sensitive identifiers contain categories of personal data specified in data protection legislation concerning racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religion or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health, sexual life or orientation, or genetic or biometric data for identifying a natural person. Other information may also be sensitive by nature. Sensitivity can be assessed by, for instance, considering whether the phenomenon is taboo or how much the disclosure of the information could provide harm to a person, organisation or other unit of observation.

⁴ Describe if you want to anonymise this identifier, what anonymisation technique you want to use and why this is a necessary and suitable anonymisation technique.

Major	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. The anonymity of graduates is best maintained by limiting information about the major subject, as when combined with other information, they provide information about the graduate that is too individual.
Starting year of study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Classified every two years and forming a separate group of at least 20 students from all those who have studied the longest, e.g. "those who started before xxxx". The classification is most commonly made as follows: the first two categories every two years, the third every three years, and the fourth the rest. The classification starts from the most recent year. In older datasets, the variable has been classified every three years due to greater variation in values. The starting year of studies is classified so that it is not possible to locate directly in which year students started their studies. The starting year of studies is important information for students compared to the year of graduation, as people often remember people who started their studies in the same year. In some fields, admissions are also so small and unevenly distributed in gender that combining years prevents the identification of rare individuals.
Occupation or job title	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Removed. In a cultural context, information related to unemployment can be assessed as sensitive information. Some job titles may only be used by a few people in Finland.
Citizenship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. The anonymity of graduates is best maintained by limiting information about nationality, because the University of Tampere graduates an average of about 60 foreign students graduate with a master's degree each year, and there are about 1-12 of them in different fields
Region	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Classified according to the NUTS-2 division into major regions: 1 Helsinki-Uusimaa; 2 Southern Finland; 3 Western Finland; 4 Northern and Eastern Finland and 5 Åland-Åland. The region cannot be left as the area variable of the place of residence, because the information could become a factor enabling identification if the snooper suspects that he or she identifies a person.

Other identifiable information

Open-ended responses	The data also includes open-ended variables, most of which are "other questions" after structured question batteries, e.g. "Your current main employer is: Other what?". The open-ended variables randomly contain information about the major subject, the starting years of studies, the exact names of exchange and internship destinations, illnesses, teachers' names, thesis topics and other random indirect identifiers. All other covariables, excluding those concerning satisfaction or dissatisfaction with teaching at the University of Tampere, shall be removed from the open variables. The variables themselves are not removed, since there is no classified
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	<p>information about them, and anonymisation can be implemented with reasonable resources. In other words, e.g. job title, open-ended questions related to alumni activities and internships, and open-ended variables for which classified data are already available and contain detailed information about the respondent's work or life situation require anonymisation. These include, for example open-ended questions such as: Current main employer: "other, what"? Which of the following most closely describes your main job: "other, what"? Employment difficulties: "other, what"? and the Language variable (what languages do you know?).</p> <p>Excluded open variables shall be anonymised so that no person or third persons can be identified through rare events, personal characteristics, titles, major, etc. Open-ended answers must not reveal the exact major subject in the smallest fields, the year of commencement of studies, separate locations of university education, rare master's programmes, names of thesis supervisors or professional titles.</p>
<p>Combinations</p>	<p>An individual cannot be directly identified on the basis of the data obtained from the data, unless he or she has provided direct identifiers in the open variables, such as a rare occupation, job or job title or a personal name.</p>
<p>Third persons</p>	<p>The questions do not directly ask for information relating to third parties. However, the data may contain data on third persons in open variables, e.g. mentions of university staff.</p> <p>The names of the university staff can be left if the person is spoken of in a positive tone. For defamatory or offensive comments, the name will be removed.</p>
<p>Future risks</p>	<p>After anonymisation, it is possible to combine the data with other datasets, such as other surveys, master's theses or data elsewhere commissioned by the University of Tampere for its students, but identification based on them is highly unlikely and finding an exact match would be very difficult. The observations in the data cannot be linked to each other with the help of any code key.</p> <p>Rare characteristics of individuals, exact job description or other information about the workplace have been anonymised from the materials so that the information of an individual person cannot be searched online, for example on LinkedIn or Facebook.</p>